

Online Companion - Affine and Exact Reformulations of Uncertainty-Aware Energy and Reserve Dispatch

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This paper serves as an electronic companion to the paper [1]. Section 1 presents the nomenclature used in the document. Section 2 introduces mathematical definitions of the different uncertainty-aware optimization models used in [1]. Finally, Section 3 presents further details of the case study, which has already been presented in [1].

1 Nomenclature

	Sets:
$g \in \mathcal{G}$:Set of generators.
$l \in \mathcal{L}$:Set of transmission lines.
$d \in \mathcal{D}$:Set of demands.
$d_s \in \mathcal{D}$:Set of demand sharing per electric node in percentage.
$z \in \mathcal{Z}$:Set of uncertainty zones coming from wind.
$w \in \mathcal{W}$:Set of wind generators.
$t \in \mathcal{T}$:Set of time steps [hours].
$s \in \mathcal{S}$:Set of scenarios.
$v \in \mathcal{V}$:Set of vertices.
	Parameters:
$c \in \mathbb{R}^{ \mathcal{G} }$:Production cost of generators [euro/MWh].
$c^+ \in \mathbb{R}^{ \mathcal{G} }$:Cost of upward reserve from conventional generators [euro/MWh].
$c^- \in \mathbb{R}^{ \mathcal{G} }$:Cost of downward reserve from conventional generators [euro/MWh].
$c_r \in \mathbb{R}^{ \mathcal{G} }$:Cost of reserve capacity [euro/MW].
$c_a \in \mathbb{R}^{ \mathcal{G} }$:Cost of reserve activation [euro/MWh].
$c_b \in \mathbb{R}^{ \mathcal{G} }$:Cost of load-shedding [euro/MWh].
$d \in \mathbb{R}^{ \mathcal{D} }$:Demand [MW].
$F_l \in \mathbb{R}^{ \mathcal{L} }$:Capacity limitations of transmission lines [MW].
$P_{\max} \in \mathbb{R}^{ \mathcal{G} }$:Capacity of generators [MW].
$P_r \in \mathbb{R}^{ \mathcal{G} }$:Maximum reserve provision capability of conventional generators [MW].
$W \in \mathbb{R}^{ \mathcal{W} \times \mathcal{W} }$:Diagonal matrix of installed capacity of renewable generators [MW].
$W_m \in \mathbb{R}^{ \mathcal{W} \times \mathcal{W} }$:Matrix of connections between wind parks and electrical nodes.
$G_m \in \mathbb{R}^{ \mathcal{W} \times \mathcal{W} }$:Matrix of connections between power plants and electrical nodes.
$PTDF \in \mathbb{R}^{ \mathcal{L} }$:Matrix of Power Transfer Distribution Factor of the electric lines.
$\epsilon \in \mathbb{S}$:Wind forecast scenarios in per unit value.
$e \in \mathbb{S}$:Error between wind forecast and the different scenarios in per unit value.
ρ	:Radius of the Wasserstein ball.

Decision variables:	
$p \in \mathbb{R}^{ \mathcal{G} }$:Power dispatch of generators in day-ahead market [MW].
$Y \in \mathbb{R}^{ \mathcal{G} \times \mathcal{Z} }$:Response of conventional generation to cover wind mismatches.
$r^{up,down} \in \mathbb{R}^{ \mathcal{G} }$:Upward and downward reserve dispatch of conventional generators [MW].
$p_p \in \mathbb{R}^{ \mathcal{G} }$:Activated upward reserve per conventional unit [MWh].
$p_n \in \mathbb{R}^{ \mathcal{G} }$:Activated downward reserve per conventional unit [MWh].
$\Delta p \in \mathbb{R}^{ \mathcal{G} }$:Total activation response from conventional power plants [MWh].
s	:Wind spillage [MWh].
b	:Load-shedding [MWh].
$\beta, \gamma, \lambda, \mathbf{z}, \mathbf{n}$:Auxiliary variables to support the proposed reformulations.

2 Mathematical formulations

2.1 Deterministic

The objective of this optimization model is to minimize the production cost (1a) based on a single-point representation of the uncertainty.

$$\min_p \sum_{t=1}^T (c \cdot p_{g,t}) \quad (1a)$$

$$s.t. \quad 0 \leq p_{g,t} \leq P_{max}, \quad \forall t, g \in T, G \quad (1b)$$

$$\sum_{g=1}^G p_{g,t} + \sum_{w=1}^W W \cdot \mu_{w,t} - d_t = 0, \forall t, g, w \in T, G, W \quad (1c)$$

$$\text{PTDF}_l \cdot (G_m \cdot p_{g,t} + W_m \cdot W \cdot \mu_{w,t} - ds \cdot d_t) \leq F_l, \quad \forall t, g, w, l \in T, G, W, 2L \quad (1d)$$

Three constraints are written in this model. Firstly, the limitations of each power plant's minimum and maximum power capacities are specified in constraint (1b), where the parameter P_{max} is a vector keeping the maximum power capacities for each power plant. Then, the energy balance is represented in constraint (1c). W is a set that contains the capacities of each power plant in its diagonal positions. It is then multiplied by the parameter $\mu_{w,t}$, converting thus the per unit forecast into MW. Finally, the maximum capacity of each electric network line is established in the last constraint. The Power Transfer Distribution Factor (PTDF) matrix indicates the incremental change in real power that occurs on the transmission lines due to the power injection in each network line.

2.2 Stochastic Optimization (Linear Decision Rules)

The objective function of this model tries to minimize the total dispatch cost for the average activation cost value (2a).

$$\min_{p, Y, r^{up}, r^{down}} \sum_{t=1}^T \left(c \cdot p_{g,t} + c_r \cdot r_{g,t}^{up} + c_r \cdot r_{g,t}^{down} + \sum_{i=1}^S \frac{Y_{g,w,t} \cdot e_{w,t,s}}{S} \right) \quad (2a)$$

$$s.t. \quad 0 \leq p_{g,t} \leq P_{max}, \forall t, g \in T, G \quad (2b)$$

$$\sum_{g=1}^G p_{g,t} + \sum_{w=1}^W W \cdot \mu_{w,t} - d_t = 0, \forall t, g, w \in T, G, W \quad (2c)$$

$$\text{PTDF}_l \cdot (G_m \cdot p_{g,t} + W_m \cdot W \cdot \mu_{w,t} - ds \cdot d_t) \leq F_l, \forall t, g, w, l \in T, G, W, 2L \quad (2d)$$

$$p_{g,t} + r_{g,t}^{up} \leq P_{max}, \quad \forall t, g \in T, G \quad (2e)$$

$$0 \leq p_{g,t} - r_{g,t}^{down}, \quad \forall t, g \in T, G \quad (2f)$$

$$0 \leq r_{g,t}^{up} \leq P_r, \quad \forall t, g \in T, G \quad (2g)$$

$$0 \leq r_{g,t}^{down} \leq P_r, \quad \forall t, g \in T, G \quad (2h)$$

$$W_{w,t} + Y_{g,w,t} = 0, \quad \forall t, g, w \in T, G, W \quad (2i)$$

$$Y_{g,w,t} \cdot e_{w,t,s} \leq r_{g,t}^{up}, \quad \forall t, g, w, s \in T, G, W, S \quad (2j)$$

$$-r_{g,t}^{down} \leq Y_{g,w,t} \cdot e_{w,t,s}, \quad \forall t, g, w, s \in T, G, W, S \quad (2k)$$

$$\text{PTDF}_l \cdot (G_m (p_{g,t} + Y_{g,w,t} \cdot e_{w,t,s}) + W_m \cdot W \cdot \varepsilon_{w,t,s} - ds \cdot d_t) \leq F_l^{\max}, \quad \forall t, g, w, s, l \in T, G, W, S, 2L \quad (2l)$$

The first three constraints are exactly the same as for the deterministic model. Then constraints (2e) and (2f) limit the allocation of the maximum and minimum reserve capacities. Furthermore, constraints (2g) and (2h) restrict the reserve capacity according to the response-ability of each conventional unit. On the other hand, constraint (2i) ensures that the real-time power balance is respected. Constraints (2j) and (2k) define the reserves (downwards and upwards) to be bigger than the detected error per scenario so that it can have enough capacity to respond to the real-time expected imbalances. Finally, the last constraint (2l) ensures that the actions taken in real-time do not exceed the capacity limitations of the power lines.

2.3 Robust Optimization (Linear Decision Rules)

Robust Optimization tries to minimize the total operating cost for the worst-case scenario (3a).

$$\min_{p, Y, r^{up}, r^{down}, \beta} \sum_{t=1}^T \left(c \cdot p_{g,t} + c_r \cdot r_{g,t}^{up} + c_r \cdot r_{g,t}^{down} + \beta \right) \quad (3a)$$

$$s.t. \quad 0 \leq p_{g,t} \leq P_{\max}, \forall t, g \in T, G \quad (3b)$$

$$\sum_{g=1}^G p_{g,t} + \sum_{w=1}^W W \cdot \mu_{w,t} - d_t = 0, \quad \forall t, g, w \in T, G, W \quad (3c)$$

$$PTDF_l \cdot (G_m \cdot p_{g,t} + W_m \cdot W \cdot \mu_{w,t} - ds \cdot d_t) \leq F_l, \forall t, g, w, l \in T, G, W, 2L \quad (3d)$$

$$p_{g,t} + r_{g,t}^{up} \leq P_{\max}, \quad \forall t, g \in T, G \quad (3e)$$

$$0 \leq p_{g,t} - r_{g,t}^{down}, \quad \forall t, g \in T, G \quad (3f)$$

$$0 \leq r_{g,t}^{up} \leq P_r, \quad \forall t, g \in T, G \quad (3g)$$

$$0 \leq r_{g,t}^{down} \leq P_r, \quad \forall t, g \in T, G \quad (3h)$$

$$W_{w,t} + Y_{g,w,t} = 0, \quad \forall t, g, w \in T, G, W \quad (3i)$$

$$Y_{g,w,t} \cdot e_{w,t,s} \leq r_{g,t}^{up}, \quad \forall t, g, w, s \in T, G, W, S \quad (3j)$$

$$-r_{g,t}^{down} \leq Y_{g,w,t} \cdot e_{w,t,s}, \quad \forall t, g, w, s \in T, G, W, S \quad (3k)$$

$$PTDF_l \cdot (G_m (p_{g,t} + Y_{g,w,t} \cdot e_{w,t,s}) + W_m \cdot W \cdot \varepsilon_{w,t,s} - ds \cdot d_t) \leq F_l^{\max}, \quad \forall t, g, w, s, l \in T, G, W, S, 2L \quad (3l)$$

$$c \cdot Y_{g,w,t} \cdot e_{w,t,v} \leq \beta, \quad \forall t, g, w, v \in T, G, W, V \quad (3m)$$

The first 11 constraints of the Robust model are the same as the Stochastic model. However, this model will compute all the activation costs for responding to the expected errors. The last constraint (3m) will impose the auxiliary variable to take the maximum value from all computed vertices, thus obtaining the worst-case scenario. Finally, this will be incorporated into the minimization to ensure that it will just take the maximum value, but it will not go further(3a).

2.4 Distributionally Robust Optimization (Linear Decision Rules)

Distributionally Robust Optimization aims to minimize the total dispatching cost for the worst-case scenario over all probability distributions within the ambiguity set (4a).

$$\min_{p, Y, r^{up}, r^{down}, \gamma, \lambda, z, n} \sum_{t=1}^T (c \cdot p_{g,t} + c_r \cdot r_{g,t}^{up} + c_r \cdot r_{g,t}^{down} + \lambda \cdot \rho + \frac{\sum_{i=1}^S n_i}{S}) \quad (4a)$$

$$s.t. \quad 0 \leq p_{g,t} \leq P_{\max}, \quad \forall t, g \in T, G \quad (4b)$$

$$\sum_{g=1}^G p_{g,t} + \sum_{w=1}^W W \cdot \mu_{w,t} - d_t = 0, \quad \forall t, g, w \in T, G, W \quad (4c)$$

$$PTDF_l \cdot (G_m \cdot p_{g,t} + W_m \cdot W \cdot \mu_{w,t} - ds \cdot d_t) \leq F_l, \quad \forall t, g, w, l \in T, G, W, 2L \quad (4d)$$

$$p_{g,t} + r_{g,t}^{up} \leq P_{\max}, \quad \forall t, g \in T, G \quad (4e)$$

$$0 \leq p_{g,t} - r_{g,t}^{down}, \quad \forall t, g \in T, G \quad (4f)$$

$$0 \leq r_{g,t}^{up} \leq P_r, \quad \forall t, g \in T, G \quad (4g)$$

$$0 \leq r_{g,t}^{down} \leq P_r, \quad \forall t, g \in T, G \quad (4h)$$

$$W_{w,t} + Y_{g,w,t} = 0, \quad \forall t, g, w \in T, G, W \quad (4i)$$

$$\sum (c \cdot Y_{g,w,t} \cdot e_{w,t,s} + \gamma_{g,s'} \cdot (d' - C' \cdot e_{w,t,s})) \leq n_s, \quad \forall t, g, w, s \in T, G, W, S \quad (4j)$$

$$\sum_{w=1}^W z_{s,w,t} \leq \lambda_t, \quad \forall t, w, s \in T, W, S \quad (4k)$$

$$\lambda_t \geq 0, \quad \forall t \in T \quad (4l)$$

$$\gamma_t \geq 0, \quad \forall t \in T \quad (4m)$$

$$C' \cdot \gamma_{g,s,t} - Y_{g,w,t} \cdot c \leq z_{s,w,t}, \quad \forall t, g, w, s \in T, G, W, S \quad (4n)$$

$$C' \cdot \gamma_{g,s} - Y_{g,w,t} \cdot c \geq -z_{s,w,t}, \quad \forall t, g, w, s \in T, G, W, S \quad (4o)$$

$$Y_{g,w,t} \cdot e_{w,t,s} \leq r_{g,t}^{up}, \quad \forall t, g, w, s \in T, G, W, S \quad (4p)$$

$$-r_{g,t}^{down} \leq Y_{g,w,t} \cdot e_{w,t,s}, \quad \forall t, g, w, s \in T, G, W, S \quad (4q)$$

$$PTDF_l \cdot (G_m (p_{g,t} + Y_{g,w,t} \cdot e_{w,t,s}) + W_m \cdot W \cdot \varepsilon_{w,t,s} - ds \cdot d_t) \leq F_l^{\max}, \quad \forall t, g, w, s, l \in T, G, W, S, 2L \quad (4r)$$

The day-ahead constraints from (4b) to (4i) are the same as in the rest of the codes modelled using LDR. There will be four new auxiliary variables Y, γ, λ, z, n in this model. Constraints (4j) - (4o) create the ambiguity sets. Finally, the constraints (4p), (4q) and (4r) are the same as in the rest of the models using LDRs.

2.5 Stochastic Optimization (Exact Formulation)

This model is a two-stage market-clearing model which simulates both the day-ahead and real-time market-clearing stages. The objective will be to minimize the total dispatch cost, as always. Since it has a stochastic approach, the decision variables will be optimized for the average of the considered scenarios (5a). However, this time load-shedding and spillage are also possible.

$$\min_{p, \Delta p, p^+, p^-, b, s, r^{up}, r^{down}} \sum_{t=1}^T (c \cdot p_{g,t} + c_r \cdot r_{g,t}^{up} + c_r \cdot r_{g,t}^{down} + \sum_{i=1}^S \frac{c^+ \cdot p_{s,g,t}^+ + c^- \cdot p_{s,g,t}^- + b_{s,g,t} \cdot c^b}{S}) \quad (5a)$$

$$s.t. \quad 0 \leq p_{g,t} \leq P_{\max}, \quad \forall t, g \in T, G \quad (5b)$$

$$\sum_{g=1}^G p_{g,t} + \sum_{w=1}^W W \cdot \mu_{w,t} - d_t = 0, \forall t, g, w \in T, G, W \quad (5c)$$

$$\text{PTDF}_l \cdot (G_m \cdot p_{g,t} + W_m \cdot W \cdot \mu_{w,t} - ds \cdot d_t) \leq F_l, \quad \forall t, g, w, l \in T, G, W, 2L \quad (5d)$$

$$p_{g,t} + r_{g,t}^{up} \leq P_{\max}, \quad \forall t, g \in T, G \quad (5e)$$

$$0 \leq p_{g,t} - r_{g,t}^{down}, \quad \forall t, g \in T, G \quad (5f)$$

$$0 \leq r_{g,t}^{up} \leq P_r, \quad \forall t, g \in T, G \quad (5g)$$

$$0 \leq r_{g,t}^{down} \leq P_r, \quad \forall t, g \in T, G \quad (5h)$$

$$p_{g,t,s}^+ + p_{g,t,s}^- = \Delta p_{g,t,s}, \quad \forall t, g, s \in T, G, S \quad (5i)$$

$$- \sum_{g=1}^G \Delta p_{g,t,s} + s_{g,t,s} - b_{g,t,s} = \sum_{w=1}^W e_{w,t,s}, \quad \forall t, g, w, s \in T, G, W, S \quad (5j)$$

$$\Delta p_{g,t,s} \leq r_{g,t}^{up}, \quad \forall t, g, s \in T, G, S \quad (5k)$$

$$- r_{g,t}^{down} \leq \Delta p_{g,t,s}, \quad \forall t, g, s \in T, G, S \quad (5l)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{PTDF}_l (G_m \cdot (p_{g,t} + \Delta p_{g,t,s}) \\ & + W_m \cdot W \cdot e_{w,t,s} - ds \cdot d_t) \leq F_l^{\max}, \quad \forall t, g, w, s, l \in T, G, W, S, 2L \end{aligned} \quad (5m)$$

From the constraint (5b) to the constraint (5h), this model is the same as the stochastic model using LDRs. Constraints (5k) and (5l) limit the real-time reserve actions (upwards and downwards) depending on the booked reserve capacities. These reserve actions have been divided into positive and negative actions due to the different costs they have (5i). Constraint (5j) refers to the real-time power balance. Finally, the maximum real-time capacity of electric lines is defined in constraint (5m).

2.6 Robust Optimization (Exact Formulation)

This model is similar to the stochastic model using Exact Formulation, except for the variable . The model's objective is to minimize the total cost for the worst-case scenario (6a).

$$\min_{p, Y, r^{up}, r^{down}, \beta} \sum_{t=1}^T \left(c \cdot p_{g,t} + c_r \cdot r_{g,t}^{up} + c_r \cdot r_{g,t}^{down} + \beta \right) \quad (6a)$$

$$s.t. \quad 0 \leq p_{g,t} \leq P_{\max}, \quad \forall t, g \in T, G \quad (6b)$$

$$\sum_{g=1}^G p_{g,t} + \sum_{w=1}^W W \cdot \mu_{w,t} - d_t = 0, \forall t, g, w \in T, G, W \quad (6c)$$

$$\text{PTDF}_l \cdot (G_m \cdot p_{g,t} + W_m \cdot W \cdot \mu_{w,t} - ds \cdot d_t) \leq F_l, \quad \forall t, g, w, l \in T, G, W, 2L \quad (6d)$$

$$p_{g,t} + r_{g,t}^{up} \leq P_{\max}, \quad \forall t, g \in T, G \quad (6e)$$

$$0 \leq p_{g,t} - r_{g,t}^{down}, \quad \forall t, g \in T, G \quad (6f)$$

$$0 \leq r_{g,t}^{up} \leq P_r, \quad \forall t, g \in T, G \quad (6g)$$

$$0 \leq r_{g,t}^{down} \leq P_r, \quad \forall t, g \in T, G \quad (6h)$$

$$p_{g,t,v}^+ + p_{g,t,v}^- = \Delta p_{g,t,v}, \quad \forall t, g, v \in T, G, V \quad (6i)$$

$$- \sum_{g=1}^G \Delta p_{g,t,v} + s_{g,t,v} - b_{g,t,v} = \sum_{w=1}^W e_{w,t,v}, \quad \forall t, g, w, v \in T, G, W, V \quad (6j)$$

$$\Delta p_{g,t,v} \leq r_{g,t}^{up}, \quad \forall t, g, v \in T, G, V \quad (6k)$$

$$- r_{g,t}^{down} \leq \Delta p_{g,t,v}, \quad \forall t, g, v \in T, G, V \quad (6l)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{PTDF}_l (G_m \cdot (p_{g,t} + \Delta p_{g,t,v}) \\ & + W_m \cdot W \cdot e_{w,t,v} - ds \cdot d_t) \leq F_l^{\max}, \quad \forall t, g, w, v, l \in T, G, W, V, 2L \end{aligned} \quad (6m)$$

$$c^+ \cdot p_{v,g,t}^+ + c^- \cdot p_{v,g,t}^- + b_{v,g,t} \cdot c^b \leq \beta, \quad \forall t, g, v \in T, G, V \quad (6n)$$

All the constraints from (6b) to (6m) are exactly the same as in the stochastic model. There is only a new constraint (6n), which specifies the value of β . In this constraint, the cost of taking real-time actions is computed for all possible vertices. The variable β will take the maximum value, thus obtaining the worst-case scenario.

2.7 Out-of-sample (Testing model)

To compare the results of each optimization technique on a fair basis, an extra model has been created. The decisions from day-ahead variables from previous models were inserted as parameters in this testing model. The model will try to find the best response from the flexible power plants to address the unbalance in demand and production, trying to minimize the total dispatch cost. This model will have the opportunity to use the scheduled reserves (coming from the decisions taken in the in-sample models) or to use the variables spillage and load-shedding.

$$\min_{\Delta p, p^+, p^-, b, s, r^{up}, r^{down}} \sum_{t=1}^T (c \cdot p_{g,t} + c^+ \cdot p_{g,t}^+ + c^- \cdot p_{g,t}^- + b_{g,t} \cdot c^b) \quad (7a)$$

$$s.t. \quad - \sum_{g=1}^G \Delta p_{g,t} + s_{g,t} - b_{g,t} = \sum_{w=1}^W e_{w,t}, \quad \forall t, g, w \in T, G, W \quad (7b)$$

$$p_{g,t}^+ + p_{g,t}^- = \Delta p_{g,t}, \quad \forall t, g, w \in T, G, W \quad (7c)$$

$$\Delta p_{g,t} \leq r_{g,t}^{up}, \quad \forall t, g \in T, G \quad (7d)$$

$$-r_{g,t}^{down} \leq \Delta p_{g,t}, \quad \forall t, g \in T, G \quad (7e)$$

$$\text{PTDF}_l \cdot (G_m \cdot (p_{g,t} + \Delta p_{g,t}) + W_m \cdot W \cdot e_{w,t} - ds \cdot d_t) \leq F_l^{\max}, \quad \forall t, g, w, l \in T, G, W, 2L \quad (7f)$$

All the constraints are the same as in the stochastic problem modelled as EF, where the day-ahead variables and constraints have been eliminated.

3 Case study

3.1 Cost parameters

The following production costs in Tables 1 and 2 have been assumed to obtain the results in [1]:

Table 1: Production costs of the different natural gas generators [4].

Generator number	Price (euro/MWh)
1	20
2	19.5
3	19
4	20
5	18.5
6	19
7	20
8	18.5
9	20
14	20

Table 2: Production costs of the different nuclear generators [4].

Generator number	Price (euro/MWh)
10	9.5
11	10
12	10
13	10

Furthermore, the cost of reserve capacity was assumed to be 250 euros/MW [4], and the cost for load-shedding was 4700 euros/MWh [4].

3.2 Belgian electrical grid

Our case study considers a simplified version of the Belgian high voltage electrical grid as it was mentioned in [1]. In this section, we give further information about the characteristics of each electrical line and considered power generation.

Fig. 1 shows the node connection, reactance and Power Carrying Capacities (PCC) of each electrical line.

From node	To node	X [p.u.]	PCC [MW_e]	From node	To node	X [p.u.]	PCC [MW_e]
1	12	0.121	1184.7	12	37	0.010	1184.4
2	5	0.313	1295.1	12	38	0.009	1295.1
3	31	0.075	1295.1	12	39	0.011	1295.1
3	31	0.075	1295.1	13	40	0.034	1295.1
3	14	0.130	1184.4	13	41	0.139	1184.4
3	14	0.130	1295.1	14	42	0.046	1295.1
4	6	0.051	1184.4	15	16	0.046	1296.9
4	6	0.053	1295.1	15	18	0.069	1295.1
4	8	0.155	1295.1	15	18	0.069	1295.1
4	32	0.046	1184.4	16	17	0.107	1295.1
5	33	0.007	1184.4	16	18	0.115	1295.1
5	33	0.007	1184.4	17	41	0.189	1295.1
5	12	0.145	1184.4	18	42	0.112	1184.4
5	12	0.145	1373.4	19	43	0.025	1295.1
6	18	0.051	1295.1	2	22	0.044	364.5
6	18	0.050	1184.4	2	25	0.062	305.1
6	34	0.071	1295.1	2	44	0.084	305.1
6	34	0.069	1373.4	2	45	0.142	364.5
7	8	0.145	1295.1	20	26	0.026	374.4
7	12	0.106	1295.1	20	28	0.031	334.8
8	35	0.006	1295.1	21	24	0.033	610.2
8	35	0.006	1184.4	21	40	0.010	480.6
8	32	0.110	1184.4	5	23	0.081	426.6
8	19	0.041	1184.4	22	45	0.097	364.5
9	18	0.075	1184.4	23	45	0.075	426.6
9	18	0.068	1295.1	24	28	0.089	374.4
9	18	0.075	1184.4	24	29	0.022	270.0
9	36	0.024	1184.4	25	44	0.022	305.1
9	14	0.226	1184.4	26	28	0.053	334.8
10	32	0.034	1295.1	27	28	0.113	364.5
11	14	0.039	1295.1	27	30	0.080	364.5
12	13	0.140	1184.4	28	46	0.046	355.5
12	28	0.048	1184.4	29	46	0.058	355.5
12	19	0.185	1184.4	30	45	0.021	364.5
12	37	0.010	1184.4				

Figure 1: Simplified representation of the Belgian high voltage electrical grid [2].

Only three technologies have been considered as power generation sources: nuclear, natural gas-fueled power plants and wind energy. According to Elia (Belgium's electricity transmission system operator), in 2020, these three technologies accounted for a total of 88,8% of the Belgian electricity mix [3]. The characteristics of each power plant and their connections to the electrical nodes are presented in Tables 3,4 and 5.

Table 3: Nuclear power plants characteristics and connection to the electric network [2].

E-node	Pmax (MW)	Efficiency
9	3.000 / 2.935	49.30
37	1.000	49.22
38	1.000	49.13
39	1.000	49.05

Table 4: Natural gas power plants characteristics and connection to the electric network [2].

E-node	Pmax (MW _e)	Efficiency
29	188	46.84
42	663	46.92
24	451	47.01
10	513	47.09
11	465	47.18
1	350	47.26
36	384	47.35
35	405	47.43
17	422	47.52
40	86	34.00

Table 5: Wind power plants characteristics and connection to the electric network [2].

Electrical node	Capacity (MW)	Electrical node	Capacity (MW)
1	52,89	24	37,58
2	28,12	25	28,12
3	97,30	26	37,58
4	74,24	27	28,12
5	37,58	28	37,58
6	93,51	29	37,58
7	52,89	30	28,12
8	82,78	31	97,30
9	62,92	32	93,51
10	74,24	33	37,58
11	2260,00	34	74,24
12	37,58	35	82,78
13	119,79	36	92,75
14	62,92	37	37,58
15	92,75	38	37,58
16	92,75	39	37,58
17	92,75	40	37,58
18	62,92	41	119,79
19	11,61	42	62,92
20	37,58	43	82,78
21	37,58	44	28,12
22	28,12	45	28,12
23	28,12	46	37,58

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